

Synthesis and Spectroscopic characterization of Zinc Complexes

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Abstract:

In this report, we synthesized Zn(II) complexes with the tridentate ligands which are reported in the literature. Synthesized complexes were characterized by using spectroscopic techniques like ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR.

1. Introduction:

Metal and metal complexes play an important role in biological life processes, which are important ingredients in life [1]. Metal complexes are widely used in pharmaceutical, biochemical and bioinorganic chemistry as bioactive compounds [2]. Zinc and iron are the most abundant elements in the cellular body [3].

The most common structure of zinc complexes is tetrahedral which is clearly connected with the fact that the octet rule is obeyed in these cases. Zn^{2+} is a class, a acceptor in the classification of Ahrlund, Chatt and Davies [4], and SO forms stronger complexes with the first row donar atoms oxygen or nitrogen than with second row sulfur or phosphorus. In terms of HSAB theory Zn^{2+} is a hard acid. The polarizing effect of Zn^{2+} is the main reason why zinc is found in enzymes such as carbonic anhydrase.

Biological role of zinc: Zinc is an essential trace element and is a co-factor in the operation of many enzymes such as lactic dehydrogenase [5]. In plants, zinc ions activate carboxylases and leaves may be malformed if there is a zinc deficiency in plants [6,7].

In this report particularly we mainly concentrate on synthesis of zinc complexes with the ligands L1 and L6 which contains thiazole moiety.

i.e L1= 4-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)-2,6-di(thiazole-yl)pyridine , L6= 4-(2,4,6-trimethoxyphenyl)-2,6-di(thiazole-yl)pyridine

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2. Experimental

Synthesis of zinc Complexes with 4-(2,3-dimethoxyphenyl)-2,6-di(thiazole-yl)pyridine (L1) ligand:

In a three-neck round bottom flask 0.1730g of L1 taken, stirred it by adding methanol which is reported in [8]. To this, chloroform was added dropwise until the ligand completely dissolves to give clear solution. After the completion of half an hour 0.05g (0.000227mmol) $Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were dissolved in methanol (5.0ml) in a separate vials was added dropwise to a hot methanolic solution of L1 which were refluxed at $50^\circ C$. The resulting solution was further refluxed for 12 hours at the same temperature. Yellowish white color solid were obtained zinc complexes and are recrystallized by using ethanol. Same procedure followed by taking ligand L6 to get the zinc complexes. These complexes were characterized by spectroscopic technique like 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of Zn (II) Complexes with ligands L₁ and L₆

Figure 1: Structure of the synthesized compounds

3. Spectral Analysis:

3.1 ¹H NMR Spectra:

In the proton NMR spectrum of complexes ZnL₁ and ZnL₆. The peaks shifted towards the down field after the complexation. All the peaks related to methoxy proton observed as singlets at 3.4 to 3.9 ppm. Pyridine ring proton observed at 8.225 ppm as a singlet.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, d₆-DMSO): δ 8.400 (s, 2H), 7.927-7.935 (d, 2H, J = 3.2 Hz), 7.462-7.469 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz), 7.126-7.166 (t, 1H, J = 7 Hz, ArH), 7.073-7.097 (d, 1H, ArH), 6.994-7.018 (d, 1H, ArH), 3.919 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.730 (s, 3H, OCH₃);

Figure 2: ¹H NMR spectrum of L¹

^1H NMR (400 MHz, d₆-DMSO): δ 8.259 (s, 2H, H^{B3,5}), 7.997-8.002 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{A4}), 7.892 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{A5}), 7.486-7.507 (d, 1H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{C4,6}), 6.674-6.729 (t, 1H, J = 3.6 Hz, H^{C5}), 3.825 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.818 (s, 3H, OCH₃).

Figure 3: ^1H NMR spectrum of ZnL₁

^1H NMR (400 MHz, d₆-DMSO): δ 8.186 (s, 2H), 7.901-7.909 (d, 2H, J = 3.2 Hz), 7.428-7.437 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz), 6.199 (s, 2H, ArH), 3.861 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.773 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.728 (s, 3H, OCH₃);

Figure 4: ^1H NMR spectrum of L₆

^1H NMR (400 MHz, d₆-DMSO): δ 8.277 (s, 2H, H^{B3,5}), 8.028-8.036 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{A4}), 7.924-7.931 (d, 2H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{A5}), 7.319-7.341 (d, 1H, J = 2.8 Hz, H^{C3}), 6.961-6.983 (d, 1H, J = 3.2 Hz, H^{C5}), 3.860 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.818 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.704 (s, 3H, OCH₃).

Figure 5: ¹H NMR spectrum of ZnL₆

3.2 ¹³C NMR Spectra:

In the ¹³C NMR spectrum of complex ZnL1 the peaks shifted to down field when compared to the spectrum of ligand, which shows the formation of complexes. Aromatic carbons observed at (ppm) 168.853, 153.179, 150.961, 148.762, 146.923, 144.141, 132.466, 124.332, 122.017, 121.637, 120.626 respectively for various carbon atoms. Whereas methoxy carbons observed at 61.083, 56.053. The peak around 113.543 observed which corresponds to the carbon adjacent to the methoxy groups. The electron donating nature of methoxy group shifts the signal towards up field.

In the ¹³C NMR spectrum of complex ZnL6 the peaks at 169.495, 161.179, 158.961, 150.762, 145.923, 143.141, 143.466, 123.332, 122.017, 121.637, 118.626, 118.543 corresponds to aromatic carbons. The peak at 90.689 which corresponds to the carbon adjacent to the methoxy groups. Whereas the methoxy carbons observed at 55.849, 55.518, 55.363.

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, δ ppm): 168.853, 153.179, 150.961, 148.762, 146.923, 144.141, 132.466, 124.332, 122.017, 121.637, 120.626, 113.543, 61.083, 56.053;

Figure 6: ¹³CNMR spectrum of L1

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ ppm): 167.948, 162.315, 158.248, 150.932, 148.938, 144.871, 131.561, 123.632, 120.081, 118.758, 106.606, 99.630, 56.374, 55.917;

Figure 7: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of ZnL₁

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ ppm): 169.495, 161.179, 158.961, 150.762, 145.923, 143.141, 143.466, 123.332, 122.017, 121.637, 118.626, 118.543, 90.689, 55.849, 55.518, 55.363.

Figure 8: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of L₆

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, δ ppm): 167.822, 155.203, 151.710, 151.117, 148.685, 144.956, 125.101, 124.128, 123.788, 119.954, 109.126, 61.657, 61.035, 56.481;

Figure 9: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of ZnL_6

Conclusion:

The ZnL_1 and ZnL_6 complexes were synthesized in good yield and characterized and confirmed by using spectroscopic techniques like ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR.

Conflict of interest:

Authors hereby declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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